

Indo Anglican Writing on Indo-Anglican Fiction*(A Case Study)*

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ABSTRACT

Indo-Anglian Literature forms an integral part of English Literature, and it has attained a distinct place in the literary landscape of India. No doubt, efforts have been made in the recent past by pioneering critics of Indo-Anglian Literature & Authorship in India, and about latest Indian Writing in English to create an awareness of Indo-Anglian. Moreover, Indo-Anglian Writing has reasons to grow like American Literature or Australian Literature or Canadian Literature. The only difference between the two being that while other Literature are the products of English-Speaking people, Indo-Anglian Literature is written by Indian whose mother tongue is not English. So, this paper is an attempt to show case the commanding influence and to acknowledge their efforts pertaining to English Literature in terms of eminence and prominence for being the non-native speakers of English.

Introduction

Indo-Anglian Literature is written by Indians whose mother tongue is not English. That is why Dr. Meenakshi Mukherjee says, this condition doesn't obtain in India because much of Indo-Anglian fiction is written in language of the writer nor is it the language of daily life of the people about whom the novels are written there by double complication involved, making Indo-Anglian Literature a phenomenon of world Literature without a parallel in the world.

The important thing or point is how the writers experience characters but not how the characters experience the world. The works which the Indo-Anglian writers have created show that they have experienced the world in English. Many Indians quite genuinely think in English especially on modern conceptual problems.

Influence of British Power

With the consolidation of British power in India, English the language of rulers, began to rule on the intellectual life of people. English became a fascination and to have good command of it was oriented towards finding lucrative jobs as English came to be regarded as having a status in society. It is obvious that English provided Indian intellectuals to have a look at the world and created a Bridge between India and European nations. It also provided common medicine of evaluation. There were many educated young men who studied English with devotional preserve and respect for their own cultural heritage. Such men were a few but qualitatively their attainment in various fields were of high order.

The cultural contacts between the two countries even win both into being Political relations or never one-sided India offered to British elite Kaleidoscope Panorama of life, a very gated patron of customs, manners and traditions a rich wealth of philosophy literature and culture. Orientalists like Sir William Jones, Keith and Wilson brought before the western world India's cultural heritage. Vivekananda, Tagore, Aurobindo gave the West, the perennial message of Indian philosophy. But it is highly gratifying to note that there has been a steady increase in the study of Indian English and as a surface of academic study. Indian English literature was for long neglected till 1907, The term Anglo Indian literature used by Anglo-Indian writers were just English writers on Indian themes. But now the term Indian English Literature has come to be accepted in usage to the Literature produced by Indian in English. It is getting attention and recognition.

One may copy the idiom, but not the atmosphere. Language has got necessary tune to atmosphere and spirit. That is why, Raja Rao, the reputed novelist in his preface to *Kanthapura* says "One has to convey in a language that is not one's own, the spirit that is one's own has to convey in the various shades and omission of elevation through movement that looks maltreated in an alien language ... English is not really an alien language to us. It is the language of intellectual make-up like Sanskrit ... but not of a emotional make-up like Sanskrit or Persian...

After language, the next problem is that of style, the tempo of Indian life must be infused into English even as the tempo of American or Irish. Life has gone into the making of theirs. We can write only as Indians but with our spirits tuned to humanity at large. We may go further and even state that "We should write only as Indians".

Sri Aurobindo, Tagore, Toru Dutt, Radha krishnan, Gandhi, Nehru and Neeraj Chaudhary all were versatile writers and attained fame through the inspiring and invaluable workmanship in the field of prose, poetry, and drama, but the only possible literary form through which a writer can hope to keep honesty in constant touch with the common readers is fiction. Usually, writers get themselves established through this novel technique. That is why, the bulk of Indo-Anglian literature is in the novel form. Most of Indo-Anglian novels are conceived and created in English. The first Indian

novel to be published in English was Rajmohan's Wife in 1864. Although, writing of poetry was on the ascent, the novel established itself, both in quality and quantity. In the 19th century fiction, writing was rather limited. The first English novel by an Indian was that of Toru Dutt named Bianca or the Young Spanish Maiden. Thus, Indo-Anglian novel made a deficient appearance in 1920s, then gradually gathered confidence and established itself in the next two decades.

Conclusion

There are Indian men and women who write English well enough to find publishers in England or the United States. Their works are read by people who believe that nationals of a country are better informed than foreigners. Some have won acclaim from critics. But most critics adopt charitable attitude towards Indian writing in English than do towards their own writers. Indo-Anglian literature never heard of it. It should not be mistaken that Indian writers write in English to cater to the Westerners demands for information about the Indian scene, about Indian thought or view of the life, but he does it to pour out his soul, his vision, his insight into his reality, only to share it with man. Even more than men, women writers are gifted with fine talents and have made marks in English literature, a matter of pride to us and a source of information to the foreigners. By and large, the growing interest in West by the publishers as well as the readers is a sure sign of progress and continued hope of achievement in the field of Indo-Anglian literature.

References

1. Prof. K. R. Srinivas Iyengar: Indian Writing in English Page-11
2. Dr. (Mrs.) Meenakshi Mukherjee: The Twice born fiction, Page-24
3. B. Bhattacharya: Indo-Anglian (from the novel in Modern India) Page-43
4. James H. Cousin: The Renaissance in India (1918) Page-179-180
5. C D Narsimhaih: The Swam & The Eagle Page-1